

CCG POLICY BRIEF

Economic Data Gaps & Challenges for Energy Systems Modelling: Gas Power

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Summary

Gas-fired power generation, despite receiving criticism for its label as a “transition fuel”, has contributed to reductions in the carbon intensity of electricity in many countries over recent decades. To enable their future use as a low-carbon source of dispatchable power, new gas-fired plants must integrate biomethane, low-carbon hydrogen, or carbon capture and storage technologies, which are important technologies for many countries’ energy and climate strategies.

These strategies heavily rely on technical insights from energy system models (ESMs) to determine the role of both unabated and retrofitted (e.g., equipped with carbon capture) gas-fired power generation, using modelling tools such as OSeMOSYS. However, these insights are very sensitive to assumptions over the capital and operating costs of gas-fired power generation. In countries with limited empirical data on gas-fired power generation, there are substantial challenges in the selection of accurate cost assumptions, which could impair the usefulness of their insights. Here, we discuss how global ranges taken from the open literature could be used to define and justify assumptions over regarding the cost of gas power.

Key Policy Recommendations

- The deployment of new gas-fired power generation capacity should be coupled with a clear plan for future abatement options, to avoid asset stranding and to deliver on climate commitments.
- The sensitivity of energy system models (ESMs) to the costs of gas power needs to be accounted for when these tools are used to provide technical insights for policy frameworks and/or NDCs.
- Academic researchers, government ministries, and other stakeholders operating in countries which lack empirical data on the costs of deploying gas power need to clearly present and justify cost assumptions used for ESMs.

Economic Data Gaps and Challenges for Energy Systems Modelling of Gas Power

Introduction

Gas-fired power has a role to play in the clean energy transition, through both providing backup power generation to variable renewables like wind and solar energy and enabling a move away from more carbon-intensive fuels such as coal or oil, especially when paired with technologies such as carbon capture, utilisation, and storage (CCUS). The International Energy Agency (IEA) predicts in its Net Zero Emissions by 2050 Scenario that the installed gas-fired power capacity equipped with CCUS globally could increase to 89 GW by 2050, whilst unabated gas-fired power capacity falls by over 67% from 1,875 GW in 2022 to 611 GW in 2050 [1].

Russia's invasion of Ukraine in 2022 led to a rapid fall in demand for natural gas across the European Union, as countries tried to transition away from gas at a time of record high prices. However, plans for new oil- and gas-fired power plants grew by 13% in 2023, driven mainly by China and other countries in Asia [2]. The costs of deploying new gas-fired power generation vary substantially across countries, with the IEA assuming a cost of 1,000 USD/kW in the USA and European Union, nearly double the cost of 560 USD/kW in China. So estimating the costs of gas-fired power in countries without prior deployment must be done with care.

Previous research has highlighted the role that switching to gas from other fossil fuels could have in rapidly decreasing carbon emissions as a stepping stone towards a low-carbon energy system [3]. Many countries, including the UK [4] and South Africa [5], are looking at constructing new gas-fired power capacity in the next decade. However, whilst sources such as the International Renewable Energy Agency and the IEA [6] publish their assumptions used to calculate the costs of gas power at a regional and country specific basis, there are few sources which collate data from a wide range of sources globally. Research that does examine the impact of a range of different geographic costs is typically limited to using assumptions or data taken from select major sources [7] and often has a limited geographic coverage.

This policy brief outlines a curated dataset that presents global ranges of the technoeconomic parameters (e.g., capital costs, operating costs) which are key to modelling the cost of gas power, drawn from the open and grey literature. The aim of this brief is to discuss the challenges around data availability for gas power, especially in the Global South, whilst providing energy system modellers and other stakeholders with a method of situating and justifying their cost assumptions in the absence of empirical data to support future strategies for a phase out of unabated gas power.

Drawing upon the existing literature base

Technoeconomic data on gas power were gathered to inform the assumptions used in large-scale energy systems modelling tools such as the OSeMOSYS [8]. Relevant data were collected from websites, reports, academic articles, and databases of national and international organisations. The data covers the range of parameters needed for the technoeconomic analysis of gas power deployment, including including operating costs, capital costs, construction times and total operational lifetime.. The database has been made openly accessible in the Zenodo Data Repository and can be accessed via the following link:

<https://zenodo.org/records/11613350>. The dataset shared on the Zenodo link contains the sources that were used to populate the database

Global current capital costs for gas power

Error! Reference source not found. shows the range of overnight capital costs for the deployment of gas power, taken across 2020–2024. The costs extracted from the open literature between 2020–2024 show substantial variation, with a median value of 659, 1,060 and 2,853 for open-cycle, closed-cycle and carbon capture equipped gas power, respectively. Data that were found in the open literature were predominantly from countries in Asia, Europe, Oceania, and North America, with substantial data gaps for the rest of the world. The cost of building new capacity equipped with CCUS was nearly triple the median cost of unabated closed-cycle gas turbines (CCGT), highlighting the high costs facing the use of carbon capture to reduce emissions from gas power.

Figure 1: Range of a) capital costs and b) fixed operating costs for gas-fired power stations in 2020–2024, by category and stated in 2023 US dollar terms. The lower and upper bounds of each shaded box represent the lower and upper quartile of the data (25th and 75th percentile respectively), with the central line representing the median. Whiskers represent the range of values falling within 1.5 times the inter-quartile range, and outliers are shown with diamonds. The 25th, 50th, and 75th percentile values are written to the left of each bar. NB: OCGT refers to Open Cycle Gas Turbines, whilst CCGT refers to Closed Cycle Gas Turbines

Using global ranges to address empirical data gaps

Gas-fired power may play a limited role as a transition fuel in the global energy system over the next few decades, providing a backup for variable renewable energy sources, like wind or solar, and a source of low-carbon dispatchable power, when combined with CCUS. The IEA predicts in its Stated Policies Scenario that demand for natural gas from unabated power stations will fall from 57 EJ in 2022 to 49 EJ in 2050, though demand from China and other emerging market and developing economies will continue to rise in absolute terms beyond 2030 [1].

Understanding the current and future costs of deployment will be key to the effective design of policy support to avoid asset stranding and support the retrofitting of gas-fired power in the future. In regions where unabated gas-fired power is still being deployed, accurate estimates of the costs of deployment will be key to the development of integrated climate and energy strategies. Error! Reference source not found. shows the range of capital costs between 2020–2024 by region (where available) and projected global costs in 2030 and 2050. As demonstrated by **Error! Reference source not found.**, many countries and regions across the globe have uncertainty over the cost of gas power, especially when considering the future cost of stranded assets. This causes data availability issues for technoeconomic parameters such as installation or financing costs that are key to the effective understanding of the costs of deploying gas power. These data gaps create significant difficulties for energy system modellers around the selection and justification of cost assumptions for gas power.

Figure 2: Range of capital costs for gas-fired power stations in a) 2020–2024 for each world region, where available, and b) global projections for 2030 and 2050. Costs are stated in 2023 US dollar terms.

In countries and regions with limited empirical data on the costs of gas-fired power, it is important for energy system modellers to clearly highlight the cost assumptions used in power and energy system modelling, as the decarbonisation pathways and technical insights developed from modelling may be highly sensitive to the costs of gas power. Transparent documentation of assumptions and methodologies will also increase confidence in the modelling results, facilitating informed decision-making by policymakers and other stakeholders. The ranges presented in **Error! Reference source not found.** are intended to serve as a useful tool to situate assumptions in energy system models (ESMs) for these countries against empirical data taken from other countries and regions, addressing the data gaps whilst still providing robust technical insights to support the development of energy and climate strategies by policymakers.

Prioritising transparency and data sharing amongst stakeholders will also be essential to enhance the accuracy and utility of ESMs. By openly sharing data and methodologies, academic researchers, government ministries, industry professionals, and other stakeholders can work collaboratively to address data gaps, compare and contrast their assumptions, and so improve the reliability of energy system modelling outcomes. Given the potential sensitivity of ESMs to the costs of gas power, energy system modellers should also conduct sensitivity tests to assess the robustness of their models. Understanding how variations in cost assumptions impact model outcomes will be crucial for making informed decisions and developing resilient energy transition pathways, and situating their assumptions against the global cost curve could be a useful way of exploring model sensitivities.

However, whilst the global ranges from the open literature presented in this work can provide valuable insights and offer a way to address empirical data gaps, they should complement, not replace, direct engagement with private sector stakeholders. Collaborating with industry partners can enrich data collection efforts and ensure that ESMs accurately reflect real-world conditions and the true costs of gas power.

Conclusions

Addressing the challenges of data availability for gas power will be critical to accelerating the energy transition, particularly in countries in the Global South where there may be limited empirical data on the costs of deploying gas-fired power. By recognising the importance of assumed costs to the development of energy and climate strategies and the sensitivity of ESMs to assumptions over the costs of gas power, stakeholders can enhance the accuracy and reliability of their technical insights. Accurate understanding of the costs of deployment will be crucial to navigating the phase out of unabated gas from the power system, especially in regions which are still deploying new capacity. Whilst global ranges from the open literature can serve as useful reference points, engaging with private sector stakeholders will be essential for understanding and capturing the complexities of real-world deployment scenarios.

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